

Original Article

Evaluation of Oral Health Related Quality of Life in Patients Undergoing Hemodialysis

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Abstract :

Background : The incidence of chronic kidney disease continues to rise and, as a consequence, increasing numbers of individuals with such disease will probably continue to require oral health care. The study was done with aim of evaluating OHRQoL in patients undergoing haemodialysis in all aspects including physical, psychological, social and functional in a rural hospital of India. **Study Design:** -The study was conducted to determine oral health in patients undergoing hemodialysis as well as to evaluate the effect of oral health on quality of life within this group. The study evaluated Oral Health related Quality of Life by means of the Oral Health Impact Profile (OHIP49). It involved 90 patients undergoing Hemodialysis. **Results:** - Mean OHIP score was 22.58(±3.75). Majority of patients fairly often thought their life unsatisfying (53.3%) and were unable to function (48.9%). Maximum of the patients very often suffered from financial liability (44.4%). **Conclusion:** -Results indicated that patients have negligence towards oral health and they do not visit the dentist. They were unaware of the effects of haemodialysis on their oral health and least concerned too. Hence, the Oral Health Related Quality of Life was low even though the participants do not complain about it.

Keywords: - Oral health; Quality of life; Hemodialysis; Chronic kidney disease.

INTRODUCTION :

According to K/DOQI (Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative) Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) can be defined as, a) kidney damage for ≥ 3 months, as defined by structural or functional abnormalities of the kidney, with or without decreased GFR, manifest by either: pathologic abnormalities; or markers of kidney damage, including abnormalities in the composition of the blood or urine, or abnormalities in imaging tests. b) GFR (Glomerular Filtration Rate) < 60 mL/min/1.73 m² for ≥ 3 months, with or without kidney damage.(1) The incidence of chronic kidney disease continues to rise and, as a consequence, increasing numbers of individuals with such disease will probably continue to require oral health care. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a universal public health problem. In India, diabetes and hypertension today account for 40–60% cases of CKD.(2) Prevalence of stage III CKD is reported to be higher (6.3%). Among all the systemic

disorders, diseases of the renal system pose a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, as the kidneys are vital organs for maintaining a stable internal environment that is homeostasis. The most common reasons for Chronic Kidney Disease are diabetic nephropathy, glomerulonephritis, interstitial nephritis (including pyelonephritis), hypertension or vascular disease, hereditary or congenital disease and neoplasm.(3) The treatment of CKD includes dietary changes, correction of systemic complications, and dialysis or renal graft receipt.(4) Most affected patients receive hemodialysis for up to 4 hours, 2 to 3 times a week. Symptoms appear and induce substantial changes in lifestyle from the early stages of the disease to the treatment such as hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis, or renal transplantation. They go from a situation of normal life to a state of mortal danger or life without health that requires dialysis to stay alive. There are many aspects that affected patients will feel altered. The Well-Being - The repetition and frequency of dialysis procedure constantly reminds one of the diseases, favouring self-analysis that exaggerates physiological phenomena. The dietary restrictions are perceived and are often ignored as the deprivation of the last "pleasure" that patients keep. Body Image - Issues like skin colour, body odour, loss of urinary function, sexual impotence, internal arteriovenous fistula or peritoneal catheter presence, scars, or abdominal distension lead patients to perceive their bodies negatively and with inferiority feeling. And these feelings will limit the social and family relationships, encouraging introversion. Autonomy - The frequency of dialysis interferes and limits the lifestyle of patients. The Mental Attitude - Anxiety is always in the background due to

Abbreviations:

OHRQoL- Oral Health-related quality of life;
K/DOQI- Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative
CKD- Chronic Kidney Disease
GFR- Glomerular Filtration Rate
OHIP- Oral health Impact Profile

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daily contact with the disease and the risk of death. And that anxiety leads to distress, somatisation, obsessive attitudes, depression, aggression, and so forth.(5-8) The advancing age of the dialysis population and greater comorbidity is a fact, and the close relationship between HRQOL and mortality score confirms the importance of including quality-of-life markers in the clinical management of patients. Oral manifestations observed in chronic kidney disease are altered taste, gingival enlargement, xerostomia, parotitis, enamel hypoplasia, delayed eruption, various mucosal lesions like hairy leukoplakia, lichenoid reactions, ulcerations, angular cheilitis, candidiasis etc. Uremic Stomatitis: can be seen due to presence of markedly elevated levels of urea and other nitrogenous wastes in the blood stream of chronic kidney disease patients. This clinically appears as white plaques distributed predominantly on the buccal mucosa, floor of the mouth and tongue. Patients usually complain of pain, unpleasant taste and burning sensation with the lesions, and the clinician may detect an odour of ammonia or urine in the patient's breath.(9) Factors affecting oral health related quality of life: a) function- mastication and speech. b) Psychological- appearance and self-esteem. c) social-intimacy and communication. d) Pain/ discomfort- acute and chronic.(10) Xerostomia or dry mouth, is a frequent complaint among dialysis patients.(11) CRF can also affect oral tissues and lead to gingival enlargement, alterations in salivary composition(12) and flow rate,(14) adverse effects related to drug therapy, mucosal lesions, oral malignancies, oral infections, dental anomalies and bone lesions.(14) The decreased salivary flow may be due to direct uremic involvement of salivary glands, chemical inflammation, dehydration, mouth breathing and also from the restricted fluid intake. Taste change: The cause of metallic taste in uremic patients has been reported to be due to urea content in the saliva and its subsequent breakdown to ammonia and carbon dioxide by bacterial urease. The change in taste can also be due to metabolic disturbance, the use of medication, diminished number of taste buds and changes in the salivary flow and composition.(15) Literature search showed lot of studies carried out in past which proved the effect of CKD on oral health as well as OHRQoL but there is scarcity of such researches in Indian population. Since the quality of life varies from region to region, the present study was done with aim of evaluating OHRQoL in patients undergoing haemodialysis in all aspects including physical, psychological, social and functional in a rural hospital of India.

Materials and methods: Present cross-sectional study was carried out after the ethical approval was obtained from the institutional ethical committee. The

purpose of the study was explained to the patients admitted in Acharya Vinoba Bhave Rural Hospital Sawangi (Meghe), Wardha and their consent was obtained. The study was carried out on 90 patients who were suffering from End Stage Kidney Disease with GFR <15 mL/min/1.73m² and undergoing hemodialysis. Patients who were critically ill and undergoing renal dialysis for reasons other than CKD, such as acute renal failure, accidents, trauma, snake poisoning, etc., were excluded from the study. The data was obtained using the Oral Hygiene Impact Profile 49 questionnaire. The Oral Health Impact Profile is a measuring instrument for assessing mouth-health-related quality of life in adults containing 49 questions. Individual items record important problem areas (dimensions or domains) of perceived oral health. Seven problem areas are used to group the questions (Functional Restriction, Pain, Mental Disorder, Physical Impairment, Mental Impairment, Social Impairment, Disadvantage / Disability), function, pain, aesthetics, and psychosocial influence. Each patient was given approximately 20-25 minutes to answer the questions that were filled by the investigator. No clinical evaluation was done. The data was collected during dialysis. The response was taken on a 6-point Likert Scale (Don't know=0, never=1, hardly ever=2, occasionally=3, fairly often=4, very often=5). The total impairment of a patient as a measure was therefore calculated from the sum of the individual values and can assume values for the OHIP with 49 questions between 0 (= no complaints / impairments) to 5 (= very often). The data entry was done using Microsoft Office Excel 2007 and statistical analysis was done using SPSS 11.5 and Level of Significance was kept at <0.05. Frequency (n), percentage (%) and means of OHIP-49 items were taken along with standard deviation.

Results:

Figure 1 showed the basic demographic characteristics. Out of all the participants 27% were women, 73% were men. Amongst all participants, 29% were between age group 20-35 years, 51% were between age group 36-55 years and 20% were above age 56.

Table 1 showed the frequency of functional limitation with a mean OHIP score of 21 (± 3.87). Maximum participants occasionally experienced any functional limitations like difficulty in chewing (53%), noticed tooth doesn't look right, appearance affected, worsening of taste (64%), food catching and worsening of digestion. Whereas, majority of the patients reported of hardly ever having trouble pronouncing words (47%) and stale breathe (38%). And most of the patients were not denture wearers, hence not aware of the fitting of the dentures (58%).

Table 2 showed the frequency of physical pain with a mean OHIP score of 20 (± 4). Most of the participants occasionally experienced painful aching of body (69%),

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Table 1 : Frequency of functional limitation in study participants (N %)

Variables	Don't know (0)	Never (1)	Hardly ever (2)	Occasionally (3)	Fairly often (4)	Very often (5)	Mean ± SD
Difficulty chewing	0(0%)	4(4%)	28(31%)	48(53%)	10(11%)	0(0%)	3±1
Trouble pronouncing words	0(0%)	24(27%)	42(47%)	22(24%)	2(2%)	0(0%)	2±1
Noticed tooth that doesn't look right	0(0%)	4(4%)	40(44%)	44(49%)	2(2%)	0(0%)	2±1
Appearance affected	2(2%)	2(2%)	22(24%)	52(58%)	12(13%)	0(0%)	3±1
Breath stale	26(29%)	0(0%)	34(38%)	24(27%)	6(7%)	0(0%)	2±1
Taste worse	0(0%)	0(0%)	18(20%)	58(64%)	14(16%)	0(0%)	3±1
Food catching	0(0%)	2(2%)	26(29%)	50(56%)	12(13%)	0(0%)	3±1
Digestion worse	0(0%)	0(0%)	26(29%)	58(64%)	6(7%)	0(0%)	3±1
Dentures not fitting	52(58%)	34(38%)	0(0%)	4(4.4%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1±1

Table 2 : Frequency of physical pain in study participants (N %).

Painful aching	0(0%)	0(0%)	6(7%)	62(69%)	20(22%)	2(2%)	3±1
Sore jaw	2(2%)	10(11%)	54(60%)	12(13%)	12(13%)	0(0%)	2±1
Headache	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	20(22%)	68(76%)	2(2%)	3±1
Sensitive teeth	0(0%)	8(9%)	24(27%)	48(54%)	10(11%)	0(0%)	3±1
Toothache	0(0%)	8(9%)	44(49%)	24(27%)	10(11%)	4(4%)	3±1
Painful gums	0(0%)	12(13%)	24(27%)	40(44%)	12(13%)	2(2%)	3±1
Uncomfortable to eat	2(2%)	18(20%)	14(16%)	54(60%)	2(2%)	0(0%)	2±1
Sore spots	40(44%)	34(38%)	14(16%)	2(2%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1±1
Uncomfortable dentures	54(60%)	32(36%)	0(0%)	2(2%)	2(2%)	0(0%)	1±1

Table 3 : Frequency of psychological discomfort in study participants (N %)

Worried by dental problems	0(0%)	26(29%)	40(44%)	16(18%)	8(9%)	0(0%)	3±1
Self-conscious	0(0%)	22(24%)	42(47%)	14(16%)	12(13%)	0(0%)	2±1
Dental problems made you miserable	0(0%)	24(27%)	32(36%)	24(27%)	10(11%)	0(0%)	2±1
Felt uncomfortable with appearance	0(0%)	6(7%)	28(31%)	38(42%)	10(11%)	8(9%)	3±1
Felt tense	0(0%)	10(11%)	16(18%)	48(53%)	8(9%)	8(9%)	3±1

Table 4 : Frequency of physical disability in study participants (N%)

Speech unclear	2(2%)	44(49%)	28(31%)	14(16%)	2(2%)	0(0%)	2±1
Others misunderstood	4(4%)	42(47%)	30(33%)	12(13%)	2(2%)	0(0%)	2±1
Less flavour in food	0(0%)	0(0%)	16(18%)	44(49%)	28(31%)	2(2%)	3±1
Unable to brush	0(0%)	26(29%)	24(27%)	30(33%)	10(11%)	0(0%)	2±1
Avoid eating	0(0%)	0(0%)	14(16%)	54(60%)	20(22%)	2(2%)	3±1
Diet unsatisfactory	2(2%)	2(2%)	14(16%)	54(60%)	16(18%)	2(2%)	3±1
Unable to eat (dentures)	50(56%)	28(31%)	6(7%)	0(0%)	6(7%)	0(0%)	1±1
Avoid smiling	8(9%)	12(13%)	16(18%)	42(47%)	10(11%)	2(2%)	2±1
Interrupt meals	0(0%)	12(13%)	12(13%)	44(49%)	16(18%)	6(7%)	3±1

Table 5 : Frequency of psychological disability in study participants (N%)

Sleep interrupted	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	34(38%)	48(53%)	8(9%)	4±1
Upset	0(0%)	0(0%)	6(7%)	26(29%)	48(53%)	10(11%)	4±1
Difficulty to relax	0(0%)	0(0%)	6(7%)	28(31%)	46(51%)	10(11%)	4±1
Depressed	0(0%)	0(0%)	8(9%)	36(40%)	26(29%)	20(22%)	4±1
Concentration affected	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	30(33%)	40(44%)	20(22%)	4±1
Been embarrassed	0(0%)	6(7%)	10(11%)	52(58%)	14(16%)	8(9%)	3±1

Table 6 : Frequency of social disability in study participants (N %)

Avoid going out	0(0%)	0(0%)	4(4%)	50(56%)	28(31%)	8(9%)	3±1
Less tolerant to others	0(0%)	0(0%)	18(20%)	44(49%)	22(24%)	6(7%)	3±1
Trouble getting on with others	0(0%)	0(0%)	18(20%)	44(49%)	20(22%)	8(9%)	3±1
Irritable with others	0(0%)	0(0%)	18(20%)	34(38%)	30(33%)	8(9%)	3±1
Difficulty doing jobs	0(0%)	0(0%)	4(4%)	52(58%)	26(29%)	8(9%)	3±1

Table 7 : Frequency of handicap in study participants (N %)

Your general health has worsened	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	32(36%)	30(33%)	28(31%)	4±1
Financial loss	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	22(24%)	28(31%)	40(44%)	4±1
Unable to enjoy people's company	0(0%)	0(0%)	4(4%)	56(62%)	22(24%)	8(9%)	3±1
Life unsatisfying	0(0%)	0(0%)	8(9%)	24(27%)	48(53%)	10(11%)	4±1
Unable to function	0(0%)	0(0%)	2(2%)	28(31%)	44(49%)	16(18%)	4±1
Unable to work	0(0%)	0(0%)	2(2%)	44(49%)	36(40%)	8(9%)	4±1

sensitivity in teeth (54%), painful gums (44%) and uncomfortable in eating (60%) but they hardly ever experienced sore jaw (60%) and toothache (49%). Maximum of participants fairly often experienced headache (76%). While most of the participants were not aware of the sore spots (44%).

Table 3 showed the frequency of psychological discomfort with a mean OHIP score of 12 (±4). Maximum participants were occasionally felt tense (53%) and felt uncomfortable with their appearance (42%). Whereas, majority of the patients were hardly ever worried by dental problems (44%), self-conscious about it (47%) and thought that dental problems made them miserable (36%).

Table 4 showed the frequency of physical disability with a mean OHIP score of 21 (±6). With respect to the physical disability most of the participants occasionally experienced less flavour in food (49%) thus they avoided eating (60%) which lead to unsatisfactory diet (60%) and consequently interrupted meals (49%). Majority of the patients never experienced unclear speech (49%).

Table 5 showed the frequency of psychological disability with a mean OHIP score of 22 (±4). Maximum number of participants fairly often experienced interrupted sleep (53%), upset (53%), difficulty to relax (51%), concentration affected (44%). Most of the patients occasionally felt depressed (40%) and was embarrassed (58%).

Table 6 showed the frequency of social disability with a mean OHIP score of 17 (± 4). Majority of individuals occasionally avoided going out (56%), less tolerant to others (48.9%), trouble getting on with others (49%), irritated with others (38%) and difficulty in doing jobs (58%).

Table 7 showed the frequency of handicap with a Mean OHIP score of 23 (± 4). Most of the patients occasionally experienced worsening of general health (36%), unable to enjoy people's company (62%) and unable to work (49%). Majority of patients fairly often thought their life unsatisfying (53%) and were unable to function (49%). Maximum of the patients very often suffered from financial liability (44%).

Discussion :

The primary goal of our study was to determine the Oral Health Related Quality Of Life in patients undergoing haemodialysis. Participants were least concerned about their oral health but complained about food catching, sensitive teeth and painful gums. They were not aware of oral manifestations related to chronic kidney disease. Only few were worried by dental problems. We observed that oral health was not the priority of the patients undergoing haemodialysis, which is consistent with the findings, reported by Esra Guzeldemir.(16) Hemodialysis therapy and the complex medical conditions of participants could affect the oral health which leads to influence on different aspects of oral function, social status and their appearance. Affected appearance leads to decreased social outgoing and interactions. Out of all the parameters, majority of the participants were concerned about the cost of treatment which lead to financial liability. The expense of treating people with end-stage renal disease (ESRD), renal failure uses a disproportionate share of health care resources.(17) Psychological disability, social disability and handicap were the maximally affected areas amongst all the OHIP 49 parameters. In the present study, 15.8% individuals complained about worsening of taste which is in agreement with Hajian-Tilaki study (19%)(18) and with other previous other studies.(19, 20, 21) Worsening of taste and digestion which lead to unsatisfactory diet in 20% (24% in Hajian-Tilaki study) and lead to avoidance of eating. Also they felt self-conscious (13%) and felt tense (18%), similar findings were observed by Hajian-Tilaki 15% and 18% respectively. Out of 90 individuals, 60 (67%) were totally unable to function which was contradictory with Hajian-Tilaki results (6%). Esra Guzeldemir reported that 72% people experience painful aching while in Hajian-Tilaki study it was 9%.(16, 18) Present study showed 24% participants experiencing painful aching in mouth. This is the major cause for intermittent meals and uncomfortable eating. There is lack of oral health awareness regarding

causes and consequences of tooth loss. It includes the need perceived by the patient to get the treatment done. (22)

However, there were few limitations of the present study. The responses regarding oral health may be subjected to bias, because patients may give socially acceptable responses to questions regarding oral health behaviour, because they were satisfied with their oral health as their main concern was the systemic difficulties. Also, no clinical evaluation was done in our study which may lead to biased results. Therefore, a prospective study with clinical evaluation is recommended for assessing the effect of hemodialysis on OHRQoL of the patients, including a control group (with age and sex matched participants with similar level of disabilities) for future investigations. Regular follow up and preventive dental care is recommended from the start of the hemodialysis therapy to minimize the ill-effects and to improve oral health related quality of life.

Conclusion :

Our study indicated that patients have negligence towards oral health and they do not visit the dentist on regular basis. They were not aware of the effects of haemodialysis on their oral health and least concerned too. Hence, the Oral Health Related Quality of Life was approximately low even though the participants do not complain about it. Physical disability was very high that the patients were unable to notice the deterioration of their oral health which affects both physical and psychological life of an individual. Therefore, it is necessary for the dental communities and the dialysis centre staff to keep the patients under regular follow up and preventive dental care and there should be communications between nephrologists and oral healthcare professionals in order to promote the patients oral health status.

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